

The use of matrix Q of the decomposition theory and principal component analysis for color image mapping of a scene

Keivan ANSARI,² Nader CHAVOSHI,¹ Siamak MORADIAN¹ and Saeideh GORJI KANDI²

¹ Department of Polymer Engineering and Color Technology, Amirkabir University of Technology, Tehran

² Department of Color Imaging and Color Image Processing, Institute for Color Science and Technology (ICST), Tehran

Abstract

Color scene interchange has been widely considered in manifold applications. In the present study, a new technique comprising of the Cohen & Kappauf (C-K) decomposition theory together with PCA (Principal Component Analysis) method is proposed as a practical tool for color image mapping of a scene. In this technique, the images of the target and the standard are captured under a desired illuminant/observer combination. Matrix Q of the C-K's decomposition theory is computed for the selected illuminant/observer combination. The RGB values of the images can be transformed to the corresponding CIEXYZ values using a transformation matrix. The obtained CIEXYZ values are then multiplied by the matrix Q to obtain the corresponding fundamental color stimulus (R_{fcs}). In a further step, a PCA technique was applied to the attained R_{fcs} vectors of the images. The first three PC vectors of each image was then considered as the Image Scene Mapping (ISM) matrix. Finally, the R_{fcs} vectors of the standard image were reconstructed using the computed ISM matrix of the target image. The obtained results showed that the proposed method is capable of precisely transforming the scene of one image to another.

1. Introduction

Color scene interchange has manifold applications, for example, in modifying color of old and unpleasant photos, coloring black and white pictures, scene simulation, computer graphics, industrial design, and etc. As examples, Reinhard et al. (2004) tried to transfer the color space between images using a vision-based $\alpha\beta$ color space. Welsh et al. (2002) carried out color transformation for colorization of grayscale images. Zhang et al. (2004) tried to balance color appearances amongst a group of images, such as panoramic images and object movies by the aid of color correction methods. Although $\alpha\beta$ is a non-correlated color space, but its axes do not always match to the principal axes of the real image and also lacks stability. Therefore, these techniques might give appropriate results with color similar images but cannot be a feasible choice for color dissimilarities (Saito et al, 2007).

Saito et al. (2007) applied histogram rescaling to transform color scenes between images. Based on their proposed method the scaling procedure was carried out only on the initial and terminal points of the histogram of the target and the standard images. Therefore, the shape (distribution) of the image's histogram did not totally change and probable noise significantly influenced the results.

In the present study, a new technique comprising of the use of the matrix Q of the Cohen & Kappauf (C-K) decomposition theory together with a mathematical PCA (principal component analysis) method is introduced as a practical tool for color image mapping of a scene with a high degree of precision.

2. Method

The suggested method is based on reconstructing the spectral reflectance data of the images using the C-K decomposition method (Cohen and Kappauf 1982) and applying a PCA (Johnson et al 1998) mathematical technique to change the basic color axes of a standard image to their equivalence in the target image. The simplified procedure is introduced below:

a) Estimating the spectral data of the two images (the standard image and the target image) applying C-K decomposition theory:

- Identify the spectral power distribution (E_λ) of the light source, under which the image was captured.
- Converting the device-dependent RGB values of the digital camera to CIEXYZ values (T) using a transformation matrix. This can easily be done by colorimetric characterization of the camera.
- Calculating the Q-matrix based on the used light source and a defined standard observer.
- Multiplying the Q-matrix by the CIEXYZ values to obtain the R_{fcs} (the fundamental part of the spectral reflectance data) $Q \times T = R_{fcs}$
- Computing eigenvectors and eigenvalues of the R_{fcs} matrix by a PCA technique.
- Sorting the 16 eigenvectors (e.g. for 16 spectral data at 20 nm intervals) in accord to their importance. This is carried out according to the corresponding eigenvalue of each eigenvector.
- Selecting, the first most important three eigenvectors, as the Image Scene Mapping (ISM) matrix. The other vectors would clearly give much less information or detail if any.
- Computing the weighted coefficient (α) of the PCA method for predicting R_{fcs} .
The above procedure is carried out for both standard and target images.

b) Color transforming

- The new R_{fcs} values of the standard image are reconstructed by multiplying the first 3 PC vectors of the target image by the weighted coefficients of the standard image.

$$\hat{R}_{FCS,\lambda} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha'_i \times PC_{i,\lambda}$$

- Calculation of XYZ values of the standard image from the computed R_{fcs} .
- Transformation of the obtained XYZ values in the last step to RGB values.

In this way, the color scene of the target image is transformed to the standard image.

3. Results and Discussion

The proposed method was applied for color scene transformation between images. As an example, the result of transforming the color scene of a sunset image to a cloudy sea is shown in figure 1. Figure 2 demonstrates The corresponding fundamental color stimulus (R_{fcs}) of cloudy sea and city sunset images. In addition, figure 3 and 4 show the first 3 eigenvectors of the cloudy sea and the city sunset image respectively.

It can be seen that, the proposed method can give the possibility to transform the color spaces between images. For more clarification the color gamut of the two images were calculated with the convex hull(1996) method. The obtained results are shown in table 1. Furthermore, the color gamuts of the three mentioned images are shown in figure 5. As indicated the small color

gamut of the standard image is extended after applying the proposed color transformation technique.

Figure 1: The standard image “cloudy sea” (A), The target image “city sunset” (B), and the resultant image by applying the proposed method to convert the color scene from B to A

Figure 2: The corresponding fundamental color stimulus (Rfcs) of the(a): “cloudy sea” and (b): “city sunset”

Figure 3: The first three eigenvectors of the “cloudy sea” image

Figure 4: The first three eigenvectors of the city sunset image

Table 1. Gamut volume of standard image (A), target image (B), and final image (B to A)

	Gamut Volume
Standard image: Cloudy Sea (A)	12934
Target Image : City Sunset(B)	148828
B to A	36006

Figure 5: The CIEL*a*b* color gamuts of a: the standard image (A); b: the target image (B); and c: the transformed image

3. Conclusion

It is of interest to change the color scene of an image according to a target image. This study introduced a new method comprising of spectral reconstruction by the Cohen & Kappauf decomposition theory and identifying the basic color vectors by the aid of a PCA method. In this technique, the RGB values of the standard image are transformed to the corresponding CIEXYZ values using an appropriate transformation matrix. Then, the tristimulus values are multiplied by the matrix Q to obtain the corresponding fundamental color stimulus (R_{FCS}). In a further step, a PCA technique is applied on the attained R_{FCS} vectors of the images. The first three PC vectors are then considered to be the Image Scene Mapping (ISM) matrix. Finally, the R_{FCS} vectors of the standard image are reconstructed using the computed ISM matrix of the target image. The obtained results clearly illustrated that the proposed technique has the ability to transform the scene of one image to another with a degree of precision and accuracy.

References

- Reinhard, E., Ashikhmin, M., Gooch, B., and Shirley, P., 2001. Color transfer between images, *IEEE Computer Graphics & Applications*, 34-40.
- Welsh, T., Ashikhmin, M., and Muelleret, K., 2002. Transferring color to grayscale image, *Proc. ACM SIGGRAPH* 20(3): 277-280.
- Zhang, M., and Georganas, N.D., 2004. Fast color correction using principal regions mapping in different color spaces, *Real-Time Imaging* 10: 23-30.
- Saito, R., Kotera, H., Horiuchi, T., and Tominaga, S., 2007. Scene-to-Scene Color Transfer Model Based on Histogram Rescaling, *Proc. of the International Color Association AIC'07*, Hangzhou, China 122-125.
- Johnson R.A., & Dean, W., 1998. *Applied Multivariate Statistical Analysis*, Fourth Edition, Prentice Hall.
- Cohen, J.B., and Kappauf, W.E., 1982. Metameric color stimuli, fundamental metamers, and Wyszecki's metamerism blacks, *Am. J. Psychol.*, 95: 537-564.
- Barber, C.B., Dobkin, D.P., and Huhdanpaa, H.T., 1996. The quick hull algorithm for convex hulls, *In ACM Transactions on Mathematical Software* 22: 469-483.

Address: Keivan Ansari, Department of Color Imaging and Color Image Processing, Institute for Color Science and Technology (ICST), 55 Vafamanesh St., Lavizan Exit, SayadShirazi North HWY, Tehran, Iran
E-mails: nader_ch4@aut.ac.ir , kansari@icrc.ac.ir , moradian@aut.ac.ir , sgorji@icrc.ac.ir